

ON SMARANDACHE CONCATENATED SEQUENCES I: PRIME POWER SEQUENCES

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Abstract. Let $A = \{p^n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$, where p is a prime. Let $C(A) = \{c_n\}$ denote the Smarandache concatenated sequence of A . In this paper we prove that if $n > 1$ and $p \neq 2$ or 5 , then c_n does not belong to A .

Let $A = \{a_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ be an infinite increasing sequence of positive integers. For any positive integer n , let c_n be the decimal integer such that

$$(1) \quad c_n = \overline{a_1 a_2 \dots a_n}.$$

Then sequence $C(A) = \{c_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ is called the Smarandache concatenated sequence of A . In [1], Marimutha posed a general questions as follows:

Question. How many terms of $C(A)$ belong to A ?

In this serial paper, we shall consider some interesting cases for the above question. In this part we prove the following result.

Theorem. Let $A = \{p^n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$, where p is a prime. If $n > 1$ and $p \neq 2$ or 5 , then c_n does not belong to A .

Proof. For any positive integer a , let $d(a)$ denote the figure number of a in the decimal system.

If $A = \{p^n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$, then from (1) we get

$$2) \quad c_n = p^n + p^{n-1} \cdot 10^{d(p^n)} + \dots + p^2 \cdot 10^{d(p^2)} + \dots + p \cdot 10^{d(p)} + \dots + 10^0.$$

Further, if c_n belongs to A , then we have

$$(3) \quad c_n = p^m,$$

where m is a positive integer with $m \geq n$. It implies that

$$(4) \quad p^2 \mid c_n,$$

if $n > 1$. However, if $p \neq 2$ or 5 , then $p \nmid 10^k$ for any positive

integer k . Therefore, by (2), we get

$$(5) \quad p^2 \nmid c_n,$$

wich contradicts (4). Thus, c_n does not belong to A in this case. The theorem is proved.

Reference

- 1.H.Marimutha, Smarandache concatenated type sequences, Bull. Pure Appl. Sci.Sect. E 16(19970, No.2, 225-226.